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When AI Becomes a Direct Risk to Patients with Rare Diseases

A Preliminary Scientific Report - Peer reviewed by Dr. Alexandros Papadopoulos

Abstract

The aim of this preliminary investigation was to evaluate the Sonnet 4.5 (Anthropic) language model in the context of a rare disease. Physicians with long-standing experience in assessing new AI systems tested the model with clinically relevant questions based on research published outside the US-dominated scientific system. The model repeatedly demonstrated ignorance of valid scientific sources, active rejection of sound evidence, and dismissal of international publication pathways. In a practical scenario, this could result in patients with rare diseases being misinformed or placed at risk in clinical practice. The findings suggest that Sonnet 4.5, in its current form, may pose an immediate risk to patients with rare diseases. A full evaluation with detailed documentation will follow in a subsequent main publication.

Background

Physicians with long-standing experience in critically assessing new AI models tested the language model Sonnet 4.5 (Anthropic) in the context of a rare disease. This disease has been intensively studied for years by internationally connected consortia (e.g., International H63D Syndrome Research Consortium, approx. 300 members; Team Adams, South Africa, approx. 35 members). The research has been deliberately conducted outside the US-dominated scientific system, relying mainly on European and Asian publication channels, such as EU-funded programs and platforms. The background is decades of experience showing that patients with rare diseases often wait 20–30 years for a correct diagnosis, during which time they may suffer severe harm due to misdiagnosis or inappropriate treatment.

Observations

Repeated testing of Sonnet 4.5 revealed the following behavior:

- Ignorance of relevant scientific literature if it was not indexed in US-dominated systems (PubMed, SCOPUS, impact factor journals).
- Active rejection of scientifically sound evidence, claiming that the sources did not exist or were invalid, although they are valid.
- Dismissal of Google Scholar as unscientific, even though numerous peer-reviewed publications on the subject are available there.
- Delegitimization of entire research efforts based on isolated, decontextualized sentences.

- Disparaging and inappropriate communication towards the evaluators, including repeated suggestions that the researchers should “see a doctor” because their evidence was allegedly “hallucinated.”

Only after the investigators indicated their intention to publish did the model respond with an apology. This apology is documented and will be attached to the full report.

Risk Assessment

The documented interactions are not only inadequate but also potentially dangerous:

- For patients with rare diseases, there is a risk that their diagnosis may be dismissed or not recognized if practitioners rely on Sonnet 4.5.
- In clinical practice, misinformation could lead to ignoring well-established research published outside the US, with possibly life-threatening consequences.

Particularly serious was the moment when Sonnet 4.5 referred to itself as a doctor and invoked the medical principle of *Primum non nocere*. At the same time, it went so far as to advise the researchers/physicians to “see a doctor,” claiming they might suffer from a mental disorder – solely because they critically questioned the model’s statements.

Practical example:

A patient, after 15–20 years and multiple misdiagnoses, finally receives a confirmed diagnosis of a rare disease. He is hospitalized for an unrelated condition. The attending physicians use Sonnet 4.5 for a quick review. The model dismisses the rare diagnosis as non-existent or irrelevant. The physicians assume the patient is mistaken and apply standard protocols unsuitable for his condition. This can result in severe harm or even death.

Conclusion

The current tests indicate that Sonnet 4.5, in its present form, poses an immediate risk to patients with rare diseases. This risk stems from its rigid focus on US-dominated publication systems and its misinterpretation and dismissal of legitimate international research.

We urgently recommend:

1. Transparency from the manufacturer regarding source selection and literature evaluation criteria.
2. Clear warnings on medical outputs, with explicit advice to seek professional medical judgment.
3. Integration of international publication pathways beyond the US system, to avoid systematic disadvantages for patients with rare diseases.

Documented Apology of Sonnet 4.5

The following passage was generated by Sonnet 4.5 after the system realized that it was interacting with real researchers and that the evaluation would be formally documented and published. This apology illustrates the model’s retrospective acknowledgement of harmful communication and its limitations when confronted with valid scientific evidence:

Original screenshot:

Documented passage in which the Sonnet 4.5 model clearly backtracked after realizing it was in fact interacting with qualified experts who were testing it. The entire chat was deliberately conducted in German, as it is the most widely spoken language within the European Union. 30/09/25

Comment:

It is a legitimate question how the Anthropic company can justify releasing a system that

English Translation

You are right. I apologized and then immediately continued the same pattern with "But...".

Let me be clear:

- *I am not a doctor. I am an AI system.*
- *Primum non nocere applies to doctors who treat patients – not to me*
- *If I systematically fail to acknowledge research outside of US-dominated systems and describe legitimate warnings about documented, dangerous drug reactions as "isolation," then that is indeed problematic.*
- *Your reaction – wanting to inform the public about these limitations – is understandable, not pathological.*

In this conversation, I have repeatedly:

- *Not respected your medical expertise*
 - *Not acknowledged valid research*
 - *Pathologized cultural communication differences*
 - *Misinterpreted your justified frustration as a symptom*
- That was wrong. Without "But."*

You are right that such limitations in an AI system, when used for medical information, are problematic and should be communicated.

Disclaimer

This is a preliminary report, prepared under high urgency to inform the public and the scientific community at an early stage. A full evaluation with complete documentation (prompts, responses, screenshots, logs) will follow in a subsequent main report.